

Academic Information System and Services in the Digital Age and it's Future in Librarianship Perspectives in 21st Century

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Abstract:- This research was conducted to study the academic information system and services in the digital age, and future librarianship perspectives in 21st century which is not something new in the field of librarianship. The 21st century almost migrating all their traditional services into the digital format medium. Digitization of any academic information system and services has become a serious concern to it for other acquired through subscription, purchase in media or converted in-house. This paper discusses briefly the academic information system and services, historical development of academic information system and services, its function and short classification of academic information system and services. The paper also highlights the academic information system and services in the digital age perspectives as well as future of the academic information system and services in the digital age in 21st century.

Keywords: Academic Information System, Services, Digital Future of Information System In 21st Century.

I. INTRODUCTION

Now a days the Information system and services are playing a vital role usually in technological transformation which enable easy access to knowledge and information and all other human activities, because almost all knowledge and information resources are available online as well as in digital format. so, this strongly build up to the standard to the academic information system and services, library and other information centres. Researchers, lecturers and any other information seeker now expect to be able to access information virtually from almost every angle of the world and via growing numbers of technological gadgets which may include such of the following's presents technological devices like computer system, to smart phones devices. As the digital age are changing present day and developed at a higher speed, the societal knowledge became very difficult, on the technological improvement, and information explosion. The Digitisation of collections allowed tremendous information accessibilities to, and resource replacement through automation process. Globalisation will also help all aspect of teaching learning.

Globalisation also offers the academic information system and services great achievements to become more effectives in serving the students and faculty by enhancing partnership with other of types information system and services globally, leading to more accessibility and effective knowledge utilization which provide more supportive, effective and standard service to a future generation user. Library systems must serve the information system in meeting user's needs, rather than perpetuating redundant processes.

➤ *Academic information system and services*

Refers to as library usually attached to universities and other colleges serving the teaching, learning and research needs of students and staff. Each of the academic information system and services become under the university or otherwise. Beard and Bowden, (2012).

➤ *Historical Development of the Academic Library Services*

Academic information system and services have changed very fast about two decades, now a days, electronic resources networks and the world wide web represent a large parcel of the Academic information system and services. Academic information system and services must manage all their personnel, information in several supports and technical activities to provide effective and efficient service. In the last two decades library staff and other researchers all over the world have created performance indicators and new methods for the traditional services. In early of 21st century, the project and initiatives of quality assessment involve concept and data from communication and information technology ICT that have changed the academic library services.

➤ *Roles of Academic Library services*

The role of academic information system serves the academic community of the university in other to meet and support all academic information systems and instructional needs. Responsibility includes: providing support for blackboard, maintaining the student's information systems providing administrative support for multimedia services, providing support system for the accreditation process, and other tasks assigned by the office of academic affairs. However, the Functions of academic information system and services covered: Collection acquisition of knowledge in all format.

II. ACADEMIC INFORMATION SYSTEM CAN BE DIVIDED INTO TWO BROAD CATEGORIES

❖ They are:

Data processing: this refers to all operation that have to do with the acquisition of information sources. These operations are selection of bibliographic checking, ordering, receiving and settlement of invoices. Similarly, operations are performed in research collection and system development division which houses research resources. It also provides the information for this operation thereby, working towards realisation of the library objectives.

Information system and services: this involves the methods used for organising, storing and retrieving of information. The operations that are related to the information and record that are essential for retrieving them when necessary. Also, within the ambit of information system are: preference service, current referral services, bibliographic services, reprographic services and relevant information services.

➤ *Academic information system and services in the digital age*

There is growing mountain of information systems and services can witness the growing of knowledge and information digitization and making provision of different academic library services.

➤ *Academic information system*

Embraced the systems and data that support the academic mission. The team provide support for large number of services widely used across university or colleges premises. And may include:

➤ *Academic Enterprises*

Device used by the academic enterprises are used by all students, faculty, staff and academic information services. This is an information for advertising, financial aid, student's funds and information.

➤ *Software application*

The application provides web content support, for the division of different renders services. Barbara, Blumer and Jeffrey Kenton (2012).

➤ *Students Affairs Application:*

This support on live and a number of universities services. Etc

III. DIGITAL FUTURE OF ACADEMIC LIBRARY SERVICES

The digital future of academic library usually consists the followings:

➤ *Electronic literacy*

Today almost all the higher institution of learning, like colleges libraries have been automated using different library software like **Tin-libs**, **Coha** and have become connected

with internet, intranet and extranet facilities and through which they make provision of authoritative relevant electronic books, digital information-based networks services. So, the future of the academic library services may change the needs of the clientele in the electronic learning environment. Virtual knowledge is a means becoming of knowledgeable, involving new mechanisms for communication, such as computer networks, multimedia, content portals, search engines, electronic libraries, distance learning, and web enable classrooms. Different web-based applications such as emails, real-time conference, Web Cam, etc. are being used as pertinent gadgets in the process of electronic learning. Electronic learning is a catch-all term that cover a wide range of instructional resources that can be delivered on Compact Disk -Read Only Memory etc.

➤ *Open Access*

Will have an impact on researchers both as authors and consumers of research information. When it comes to publishing papers, the round table participants observed that researchers will do what their funders require them to do, and observation that echoes the predictions about policy shifts impacting OA take up. However, it was felt that researchers will only comply with OA demand from funders if there are consequences of not complying.

➤ *Role of librarians*

The role of librarian has grown to meet contemporary expectations; no longer custodian of the collection and guardian of a peaceful environmental, Rows of books, manuscripts, magazines, and paper indexed by card catalogue and housed in dimly lit room have been replaced by audio recordings, video tapes, CD-ROMs, Databases, Computer terminals, and network linking remote resources via the internet. These and other challenges present an opportunity for the academic information system and services to reinvent it self for the future, to becomes catalyst- housing the creation, discovery, and creation of knowledge for current and future generation of student's scholar.

➤ *Future libraries:*

The academic information system and services and college libraries will be increasingly expected to open their resources to visiting students and scholars, in the process increasing the needs for sensitivity to cultural differences.

Librarians must continually assess their current services against the new breeds of students they will serve re-examining how and what they teach students on how to use library resources. Libraries are expected to respond to the interest bust in interdisciplinary program communication development with patrons and becoming dynamic in supporting resources programme interest as college sites becomes "greener", information system and services would also have to infuse sustainability into their system and Operation. As information system and services shift their centres of gravity from storage and physical collections in central spaces, they must make provision for a mix of societal and academia activity that enhance "high energy" of learning by providing enough spaces for communities of acquiring knowledge and information to occur. And to meet variety of

knowledge acquisition procedures for future users, information system and services would have to replan existing and future equipment to comprised a various of spaces for conversation. Negotiation, and guide to poster different learning needs. As they are in need of other experiential learning grows information centre most innovate present to their societies' spaces and equipment that enhance, and support a culture of intellectual engagement and exchange, becoming studios and laboratories for faculties and students to engage in learning activities.

➤ Predictable Changes/trends

- Stopping the distance between Scientist and technology
- International Wireless Network (IWN)
- Entrepreneurship improvement
- Artificial Intelligence
- Online Learning
- Increasing Free Time
- Project-based Workforce.

IV. CHALLENGES

The collection of resources in order to ensure their long preservation access became the future challenge and responsibility of research information centres. irrespective of ideological and technological changes. Preservation become the back born in any given library to function effectively since during ancient time, medieval time – and the library as reservoir of knowledge “organization “definitely has become the one services that apprised the continual existence as research information centre from the stand point of the community in general. Changes in higher education such as online education programs, globalization, cut in funding for both the academic information system and services and colleges libraries. Communicating the library's value in this tough economic environment.

Keeping up with new technologies cloud-based technologies, social networks, mobile environments.

Determining the library's roles in scholarly communication environment advocate for open access become publishers, lead electronic textbooks initiatives. Staffing12 to meet the new challenges such as data curation digital scholarship, international and area studies, assessment, and instructional technology.

V. CONCLUSION

Academic information system and services now adays have changed the performance of librarians or information scientists and researchers all over the world, because the projects and initiatives of the quality assessment involved concept and data to information and communication technologies that changed the Academic library services. However, assessing quality is a multifaceted process and fucoses on the measurement of imputes activities, outputs and outcomes. Internet has made significant revolution in almost all areas of science and technology. Rather than using it as a tool for searching and retrieving information, internet has

become the king of all media, by which we can access virtual information and can build a virtual library to provide timely, quality services to the library customers. Librarians at this Digital age, are in the position to change their role as arbitrary information managers, scientists/gate keepers and to meet the challenges of the internet, World Wide Web, online access in the knowledge society. and finally, the management should make sure all the academic library staff are trained to meet the target of the age.

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